

ED01

Welcome to the survey on voice anonymization in journalistic interviews.

This study investigates how different types of voice modification affect listeners' perceptions — especially in journalistic contexts.

Your participation is voluntary and anonymous. The data will be used exclusively for academic purposes as part of a bachelor's thesis at Technische Hochschule Georg Simon Ohm Nürnberg.

No personal information is collected. The audio/video excerpts serve only to evaluate the voice and contain no identifiable content.

The survey takes about 10 minutes. You may stop your participation at any time.

By clicking "Next", you consent to participate and agree to the anonymous processing of your responses.

IT01

Information about the survey procedure

In this survey, you will be shown short video clips from fictional journalistic interviews.

The voices of the interviewees have been technically modified using different methods.

After each clip, you will be asked to rate the voice based on various characteristics.

There are no right or wrong answers – your personal opinion is of importance.

1. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do you not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice seemed trustworthy to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The voice sounded natural to me.

|

I was able to understand the voice clearly.

|

The voice conveyed emotional expression to me.

|

The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.

|

I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.

|

I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.

|

I trust the way the medium presents the voice.

|

The voice matched the interview situation well.

|

2. How did the voice influence your perception of the interviewee?

S112

Please describe whether and how the voice influenced your perception of the interviewee.

3. What was your overall impression of the voice in this interview? S111

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

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s2

S201**4. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.** S213

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do you not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
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The voice seemed trustworthy to me.

<input type="radio"/>					
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The voice sounded natural to me.

<input type="radio"/>					
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I was able to understand the voice clearly.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

The voice conveyed emotional expression to me.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I trust the way the medium presents the voice.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

The voice matched the interview situation well.

<input type="radio"/>					
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

5. How did the voice influence your perception of the interviewee? S212

Please describe whether and how the voice influenced your perception of the interviewee.

6. What was your overall impression of the voice in this interview? S211

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

7. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview. S313

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully

agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do you not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice seemed trustworthy to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was able to understand the voice clearly.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice conveyed emotional expression to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust the way the medium presents the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The voice matched the interview situation well.

8. How did the voice influence your perception of the interviewee?

S312

Please describe whether and how the voice influenced your perception of the interviewee.

9. What was your overall impression of the voice in this interview?

S311

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

S413 **10. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.**

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do you not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice seemed trustworthy to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I was able to understand the voice clearly.

|

The voice conveyed emotional expression to me.

|

The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.

|

I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.

|

I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.

|

I trust the way the medium presents the voice.

|

The voice matched the interview situation well.

|

11. What was your overall impression of the voice in this interview?

S411

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

S412

12. How did the voice influence your perception of the interviewee?

Please describe whether and how the voice influenced your perception of the interviewee.

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R1

13. How did you perceive the four voices overall?

R101

Please rank the voices according to your personal preference, from most pleasant (1) to least pleasant (4).

Drag and drop the voice items to sort them, or use the arrow buttons to rearrange the order.

**Voice 1 - Deep
Robot Voice**

**Voice 2 - Neutral
AI Voice**

**Voice 3 -
Emotional AI
Voice**

**Voice 4 - Voice
Conversion**

Page 07

S5

S510

S501

14. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I found the voice disturbing in this interview situation.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was able to understand the voice clearly.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice matched the interview situation well.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

15. Did you feel the voice modification in this case was excessive or inappropriate? Please explain your answer. S509

If you felt the voice modification was inappropriate, please explain why. If not, you may briefly explain that as well.

16. How did the voice affect you in this interview situation? S508

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

S611

17. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I found the voice disturbing in this interview situation.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was able to understand the voice clearly.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice matched the interview situation well.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

18. How did the voice affect you in this interview situation?

S608

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

19. Did you feel the voice modification in this case was excessive or inappropriate? Please explain your answer.

S609

If you felt the voice modification was inappropriate, please explain why. If not, you may briefly explain that as well.

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S7

S710

S711

20. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I found the voice disturbing in this interview situation.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was able to understand the voice clearly.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice matched the interview situation well.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

21. Did you feel the voice modification in this case was excessive or inappropriate? Please explain your answer. S709

If you felt the voice modification was inappropriate, please explain why. If not, you may briefly explain that as well.

22. How did the voice affect you in this interview situation? S708

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

S811

23. Please evaluate the voice you just heard in the interview.

Rate the following statements on a scale from 1 = Do not agree at all to 5 = Fully agree.

There are no right or wrong answers – the evaluation is based solely on your personal impression.

Do not agree at all	Rather disagree	Neutral	Rather agree	Fully agree	don't know
The voice sounded natural to me.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I found the voice disturbing in this interview situation.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I was able to understand the voice clearly.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I clearly noticed the technical modification of the voice.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice was appropriate for this journalistic interview.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find the technical modification of the voice acceptable.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The voice matched the interview situation well.					
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

24. Did you feel the voice modification in this case was excessive or inappropriate? Please explain your answer. S809

If you felt the voice modification was inappropriate, please explain why. If not, you may briefly explain that as well.

25. How did the voice affect you in this interview situation? S808

Please describe your impressions in your own words. Bullet points are fine too.

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R2

26. How did you perceive the four voices overall? R201

Please rank the voices according to your personal preference, from most pleasant (1) to least pleasant (4).

Drag and drop the voice items to sort them, or use the arrow buttons to rearrange the order.

Voice 1 - High Pitch	Voice 2 - Low Pitch	
Voice 3 - Voice Conversion	Voice 4 - Neutral AI Voice	

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SD

27. What is your gender?SD01

- Female
- Male
- Diverse
- Prefer not to say

28. Wie alt sind Sie?SD03

- School student
- University student
- In training
- Employee
- Civil servant
- Self-employed
- Unemployed/ Seeking employment
- Other:

SD19

30. How often do you consume journalistic content (e.g., news, reports, interviews)?

[Please choose]

31. Would you like to share any comments regarding this survey or to help us better understand your responses?

SD18

Did you notice anything negative during the survey? Were any of the questions unclear or uncomfortable to answer?

Please feel free to provide a few short remarks.

Last Page

Thank you for participating!

Your responses help us better understand the perception of voice anonymization in journalistic interviews and contribute to academic discussions about technology, ethics, and media trust.

If you have any questions or are interested in the results of the study, feel free to contact me at:

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